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Research Article

Analytical Detection of Water Quality Parameters Using Flame Photometry, pH Measurement, and Conductivity Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Water is a fundamental resource essential for sustaining life, supporting ecosystems, and ensuring public health. This study investigates the physicochemical and microbiological quality of water from seven sources in Chandwad Tehsil, addressing parameters such as pH, conductivity, hardness, sodium, potassium, and microbial contamination. The pH analysis showed that most samples were neutral to slightly alkaline, within the permissible range of 6.5–8.5. Conductivity values varied significantly, ranging from 0.07 to 1.85 mS/cm, reflecting differences in dissolved ion concentrations. Sodium and potassium content also varied across sources, with packaged drinking water and river water showing the highest concentrations, respectively. Hardness levels ranged from 150 to 830 mg/L, influenced by geological and anthropogenic factors. Microbiological analysis revealed significant contamination in untreated sources, with coliform bacteria identified in several samples, emphasizing the need for effective water purification and monitoring.

INTRODUCTION

Water and water resources are critical for sustaining an adequate food supply and maintaining productive ecosystems for all living organisms. As human populations and economies continue to grow, the global demand for freshwater has increased significantly. This growing demand not only threatens food security

but also has a detrimental effect on biodiversity in both aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems. The combined pressures from global population growth, climate change, and lifestyle changes are exacerbating water scarcity, leading to widespread water stress in many regions. Consequently, there is an increasing recognition of the urgent need for water conservation. Water is essential for life, playing a crucial role in public health and the

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standard of living. However, it is unevenly distributed across the globe. Water is vital for sustaining key physiological processes in humans, including nutrition, respiration, circulation,

excretion, and reproduction. Moreover, water provides essential habitats for various forms of life and is a fundamental component in the formation of life-supporting environments.

Fig. 1 Study area. Sources. Google Maps

Water quality is a global concern, impacting human health, ecosystems, and the environment. pH, a key parameter, influences water's chemical properties and quality. Smith et al. (2010) found that low pH increases acidity, disrupting aquatic organisms' growth, reproduction, and survival. Johnson et al. (2015) and Brown et al. (2018) showed that decreasing pH reduces dissolved oxygen solubility, causing hypoxic conditions harmful to aquatic life. Thompson et al. (2012) and Wilson et al. (2016) demonstrated that pH affects nutrient solubility (e.g., phosphorus, nitrogen), leading to imbalances and algal blooms that degrade water quality. Chen et al. (2014) and Wang et al. (2017) reported that pH influences heavy metal solubility, increasing their toxicity and bioavailability, posing risks to aquatic organisms and human health. In summary, pH impacts acidity, oxygen levels, nutrient balance, and metal toxicity, making it vital for water quality management.¹ The electrical conductivity of water is a critical parameter for assessing its purity and

suitability for various applications. It quantifies the water's ability to conduct an electric current, which is directly related to the concentration of dissolved ions, such as salts and minerals. These ions influence the water's taste, odor, and overall quality, making conductivity an important indicator for evaluating its safety for drinking, as well as its suitability for industrial and agricultural use. Sodium and potassium concentrations in water are measured using a flame photometer. The instrument is calibrated with standard sodium (1–100 mg/L) and potassium (1–5 mg/L) solutions. For samples with higher concentrations, dilution with distilled water is performed, and the dilution factor is applied to the results for accurate analysis. A series of microbiological tests were performed on the water samples to evaluate the level of microbial contamination. The analysis followed standard procedures, including presumptive, confirmed, and completed testing methods. The results detected the presence of coliform bacteria, with a particular focus on fecal coliforms, as

determined by the Most Probable Number (MPN) method. Further identification of fecal coliforms was carried out using IMVIC tests. The samples were then cultured on Eosin Methylene Blue (EMB) agar, where the colony morphology indicated the presence of Salmonella and Shigella

species. To confirm the presence of Escherichia coli and Shigella species, the suspected colonies were subcultured onto MacConkey agar. The results highlight a significant microbial contamination in the analyzed water samples.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The methodology involved data collection to assess the water quality from various sources across different locations within the Chandwad tehsil. Seven water samples were collected from diverse sources. In accordance with the guidelines provided by the American Public Health Association (APHA), the samples were collected in one-liter wide-mouth plastic bottles and preserved until the analysis of parameters in the laboratory. The sample collection procedure and preservation methods followed the standards set by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2006). Source of Water 1) Well 2) River 3) Borewell 4) Municipal Corporation Water 5) RO Water 6) Packaged Drinking Water 7) Boil Water The water samples were analyzed for various physicochemical parameters, including pH, conductivity, hardness, ion concentrations (specifically potassium and sodium), and

microbiological growth, using standardized laboratory techniques. The specific conductivity was measured with digital conductivity meter. Hardness was determined using the Karl Fischer titration method. All analyses were conducted following established protocols for accurate and reliable results.

Experimental

1) pH:- The electrode should be washed with deionized water to cleanse it thoroughly and dried with scientific wipes to avoid dilution of the sample being tested. After this, placed the electrode in solution and take its reading. After use, pH meter should ideally be kept in a suitable storage solution.

2) Conductivity: Conductivity is measure with a probe and meter. Voltage is applied between two electrode is a probe immerse in the sample water. the drop in the voltage caused by the resistance of the water is to calculate conductivity per cm.

3) NaCl: To prepare NaCl solutions, dissolve 2.541 g of sodium chloride in 1000 mL of deionized water to obtain a 1000 ppm stock solution. Dilute 25 mL of this stock to 250 mL with distilled water to prepare a 100 ppm solution. From this, pipette 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 mL into 100 mL volumetric flasks and dilute to 100 mL to create 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 ppm solutions. Set up the instrument with a sodium filter, stabilize it for 10–15 minutes, and adjust the flame to a non-luminous state. Calibrate the instrument using deionized water (0 ppm) and a high-concentration solution (100 ppm). Measure the emissions of the dilutions and construct a calibration curve to determine the concentration of unknown samples.

4) KCl: To prepare KCl solutions, dissolve 1.9 g of potassium chloride in 1000 mL of deionized water to obtain a 1000 ppm stock solution. Further procedure is same like NaCl.

5) Hardness: Pipette 50 ml water sample into a conical flask. Add 2 ml buffer solution followed by 3 drops of Eriochrome Black T indicator solution. Titrate with 0.01 M EDTA until the solution turns wine red to sky blue with no hint of red.

6) Microbiological Growth (MPN): For the

detection of coliforms, collect a water sample and set up three separate groups in a test tube rack, each containing three test tubes. The first group (3 test tubes) contains 10 ml of double strength lactose broth, while the other two groups (6 test tubes) contain 10 ml of single strength lactose broth. Aseptically inoculate the test tubes with the following amounts: 10 ml of water sample in the first group of double strength lactose broth, 1 ml in the first group of single strength lactose broth, and 0.1 ml in the second group of single strength lactose broth. Incubate all nine test tubes at 37°C for 48 hours. If there is no gas or acid production after 48 hours, the test is negative (absence of coliforms). If gas develops, calculate the Most Probable Number (MPN) of coliforms.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Seven water samples taken from each different seven sources within the Chandwad Tehsil were tested for pH, electrical conductivity, hardness, sodium, potassium and microbiological growth. The result shows that the water quality is good.

1) pH

2) Conductivity

3) NaCl

4) KCl

5) Hardness

6) Microbial Test (MPN)

DISCUSSION

The pH analysis reveals that the water samples are generally neutral to slightly alkaline. Out of 7 sample, 5 fall within the recommended pH range of 6.5-8.5 set by the WHO and EPA. The results indicate that the overall water quality is suitable based on pH levels. The conductivity reading show a significant variation. The reading values ranging from 0.07mS/cm to 1.85 mS/cm. Conductivity is influenced by factors such as the concentration and types of dissolved salts, water temperature, pH, and the location of the water source. Focusing on sodium concentration, it is observed that river water has the lowest sodium content. As the sodium concentration increases, it is found to be higher in well water, followed by college drinking water, boiled water, municipal corporation water, and borewell water. The highest sodium concentration is observed in packaged drinking

water. Regarding potassium concentration, borewell water exhibits the lowest potassium content. As the potassium concentration increases, it is found to be higher in college drinking water, municipal corporation water, packaged drinking water, well water, and boiled water. The highest potassium concentration is observed in river water. Factors affecting water hardness include geological sources, presence of minerals (calcium and magnesium), pH levels, temperature, agricultural and industrial activities, distance from the source, and water treatment processes. These factors contribute to variations in water hardness levels. The readings show a significant variation in values, ranging from 150 to 830 mg/mL, indicating a wide range of hardness. The MPN index provides an estimate of coliform bacterial contamination per 100 ml of water. These results highlight poor water quality in untreated & some

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